

Superoxide ion mediated Michael addition of active methylene compounds to nitroolefins

Raghvendra Singh Raghuvanshi^{a*} and Manorama Singh^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Udai Pratap Autonomous College, Varanasi-221 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : rsr_itbhu@rediffmail.com

^bIGNOU Regional Centre, Varanasi-221 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 29 December 2010, revised 05 May 2011, accepted 07 September 2011

Abstract : Michael addition of active methylene compounds to β -nitrostyrenes using *in situ* generated superoxide ion results in the formation of Michael adduct in 72–88% yield under mild reaction conditions, at room temperature.

Keywords : Michael addition, superoxide, crown ether, nitroolefins, active methylene compounds.

Introduction

The Michael addition reaction has been one of the most studied C–C bond forming reactions in synthetic organic chemistry¹. In particular, the Michael addition of carbon nucleophiles to nitroalkenes has received great attention^{2–4}. The versatility of this reaction has numerous applications in the elegant synthesis of useful products^{5–8}. Traditionally, these reactions are catalysed by strong bases or suitable combination of amines and carboxylic or Lewis acids. In the last few years, various catalysts such as AgOTf-PPh₃⁹, Al₂O₃¹⁰, chiral catalysts^{11–17}, kaolin/KOH¹⁸, diaryl-2-pyrroline methanols¹⁹, binaphthyl-derived amine thiourea²⁰, metal-ligand complexes^{21–23} and L-proline/ionic liquid²⁴ have been employed.

In view of the above and as a part of our ongoing research on superoxide chemistry²⁵, it is wished to report the results on the reaction of *in situ* generated superoxide ion with ethyl acetoacetate or malanonitrile in the presence of β -nitrostyrenes (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

In the course of reaction superoxide ion (\bar{O}_2^-) was generated *in situ* by the phase transfer reaction of potassium superoxide (KO₂) and 18-crown-6 in toluene at room temperature and was subsequently allowed to react with Michael donors 1a/1b and acceptors 2a-d. The results are given in Table 1. As an out come, Michael acceptor β -nitrostyrenes 2a-d readily reacted with ethyl acetoacetate 1a or malanonitrile 1b to give Michael adducts 3a-g in reasonably good to excellent yields (72–88%).

A molar ratio of 3 : 1.5 : 1 for KO₂ : 18-crown-6 : substrate 2 was employed for achieving the reaction. Each

Table 1. Reaction of KO₂/18-crown-6 with ethyl acetoacetate 1a or malanonitrile 1b in the presence of β -nitrostyrenes 2a-d

Reactants	Product	Yield (%)
		78
		79
		88

Table-1 (contd.)

	72
	77
	72
	78

reaction was monitored by TLC for its completion. The products were fully identified by their physical and spectral data, which are in full agreement with the values described in literature¹⁸.

In order to optimize the yield of product from substrates, the effect of molar concentration of KO_2 and 18-crown-6 was studied in detail with particular reference to ethyl acetoacetate **1a** in the presence of β -nitrostyrene **2a**. The results of investigation are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of molar ratios on the yield of product **3a**

Entry	1a	2a	KO_2	18-crown-6	Product 3a Yield (%)
1	1.0	1.0	1.0	0	7
2	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	34
3	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	57
4	1.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	56
5	1.0	1.0	2.0	0.5	45
6	1.0	1.0	3.0	1.5	78
7	1.0	1.0	4.0	2.0	79
8	1.0	1.0	5.0	2.5	79

Based on product isolation and existing chemistry^{26,27} of $\bar{\text{O}}_2^-$, a plausible mechanism is outlined for the above transformation (Scheme 2).

Experimental

Physical measurements and materials : Potassium superoxide and 18-crown-6 were procured from E. Merck, and were used as received. Dry DMF of Aldrich, was

Scheme 2

stored over molecular sieves (4 Å) prior to use. Ethyl acetoacetate **1a** and malanonitrile **1b** were purchased from Aldrich, whereas β -nitrostyrenes were prepared according to literature methods¹⁷. Melting points were measured in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were run on a JEOL AL300 FT-NMR and chemical shift are expressed as δ (ppm), using TMS as internal reference.

General procedure for the reaction of in situ generated superoxide ion with ethyl acetoacetate or malanonitrile in the presence of β -nitrostyrenes : Sodium dried toluene (25 ml) was placed into a three-necked round bottom flask fitted with a dropping funnel, magnetic stirrer, nitrogen inlet and a Leibig condenser protected by calcium chloride drying tube. Potassium superoxide (0.42 g; 0.006 mol) and 18-crown-6 (0.79 g; 0.003 mol) were weighed under nitrogen atmosphere using an atmosbag and were transferred into the flask. The mixture was agitated magnetically for 15 min to facilitate the formation of superoxide ion. To the stirred reaction mixture, were added ethyl acetoacetate or malanonitrile (0.002 mol) and nitrostyrene (0.002 mol) successively. Nitrogen was bubbled continuously and reaction mixture was stirring magnetically for 4–8 h at room temperature until the starting material was consumed as indicated by TLC. The solvent was removed using rotary evaporator and the residue was treated with brine solution and then extracted with diethyl ether (20 ml \times 3). The combined ether extract was dried over Na_2SO_4 (anhyd.), filtered and con-

centrated to furnish a residue which was passed through column to get pure addition product **3**.

Ethyl 2-(2-nitro-1-phenylethyl)acetoacetate (3a): m.p. 94 °C (lit.¹⁸ 93–94 °C); IR (KBr): ν 2922, 1742, 1641, 1559, 1490, 1381 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.3 (3H, t), 2.3 (3H, s), 4.0–4.2 (4H, m), 4.6–4.7 (2H, m), 7.1–7.3 (5H, m).

Ethyl 2-(1-(4-methylphenyl)-2-nitroethyl)acetoacetate (3b): IR (KBr): ν 2991, 1746, 1710, 1554, 1380 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.2 (3H, t), 2.2 (3H, s), 2.3 (3H, s), 3.9–4.2 (4H, m), 4.6–4.7 (2H, m), 7.0–7.2 (4H, m).

Ethyl 2-(1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-nitroethyl)acetoacetate (3c): IR (KBr): ν 2982, 1740, 1720, 1615, 1565, 1512 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.3 (3H, t), 2.3 (3H, s), 3.8 (3H, s), 3.9–4.2 (4H, m), 4.6–4.8 (2H, m), 6.8 (2H, d), 7.1 (2H, d).

2-(2-Nitro-1-phenylethyl)malanonitrile (3d): IR (KBr): ν 2932, 2220, 1615, 1558, 1459 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 4.1 (1H, m), 4.4 (1H, d), 4.9–5.0 (2H, m), 7.3–7.5 (5H, m).

2-(1-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-2-nitroethyl)malanonitrile (3e): m.p. 96–97 °C (lit.¹⁸ 95–97 °C); IR (KBr): ν 2626, 2260, 1601, 1549, 1498, 1432, 1250 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 3.9 (3H, s), 4.1 (1H, m), 4.4 (1H, d), 4.9–5.0 (2H, m), 7.0–7.3 (4H, m).

2-(1-(4-Methylphenyl)-2-nitroethyl)malanonitrile (3f): m.p. 100–101 °C (lit.¹⁸ 99–101 °C); IR (KBr): ν 2918, 2261, 1613, 1558, 1512, 1438 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 2.4 (3H, s), 4.0 (1H, m), 4.4 (1H, d), 4.8–5.0 (2H, m), 7.2–7.3 (4H, m).

2-(1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-nitroethyl)malanonitrile (3g): IR (KBr): ν 2922, 2230, 1612, 1560, 1258, 1176 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 3.8 (3H, s), 4.0 (1H, m), 4.3 (1H, d), 4.7–4.9 (2H, m), 6.9–7.3 (4H, m).

Conclusion :

This report demonstrates the use of $\text{KO}_2/18\text{-crown-6}$ combination for efficient addition of ethyl acetoacetate or malanonitrile to β -nitrostyrenes under significantly mild conditions at room temperature.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to UGC, New Delhi for financial support.

References

1. A. Perlmutter, "Conjugative Addition in Organic Synthesis", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1992; E. D. Bergman, D. Ginsberg and R. Rappo, *Org. React.*, 1959, **10**, 179.
2. N. Krause and A. Hoffmann-Roder, *Synthesis*, 2001, 171.
3. O. M. Berner, L. Tedeschi and D. Enders, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, 1877.
4. M. Sibi and S. Manyem, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **56**, 8033.
5. D. M. Barnes, J. G. Ji, M. G. Fickes, M. A. Fitzgerald, S. A. King, H. E. Morton, F. A. Plagge, M. Preskill, S. H. Wagaw, S. J. Wittenberger and J. Zhang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 13097.
6. Y. Hoashi, T. Yabuta and Y. Takemoto, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 9185.
7. P. Li, L. Wang, Y. Zhang and G. Wang, *Tetrahedron*, 2008, **64**, 7633.
8. N. Ono, "Nitro Group in Organic Synthesis", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2001.
9. S. Shirakava and S. Kobayashi, *Synlett*, 2006, 1410.
10. R. Ballini, R. Maggi, A. Palmieri and G. Sartori, *Synthesis*, 2007, 3017.
11. F. Chen, C. Shao, Q. Wang, P. Gong, D. Zhang, B. Zhang and R. Wang, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 8456.
12. T. Okino, Y. Hoashi, T. Furukawa, X. Xu and Y. Takemoto, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 119.
13. P. Kotrusz, S. Toma, H. G. Schmalz and A. Adler, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2004, 1577.
14. H. Li, Y. Wang, L. Tang, F. Wu, X. Liu, C. Guo, B. M. Foxman and L. Deng, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 105.
15. F. Wu, H. Li, R. Hong and L. Deng, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 947.
16. K. Kwon and D. Y. Kim, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **30**, 1441.
17. J. Ye, D. J. Dixon and P. S. Hynes, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, 4481.
18. G. Srihari and M. M. Murthy, *Synth. Commun.*, 2009, **39**, 896.
19. A. Lattanzi, *Tetrahedron Asymmetry*, 2006, **17**, 837.
20. J. Wang, H. Li, W. Duan, L. Zu and W. Wang, *Org. Lett.*, 2005, **7**, 4713.
21. C. A. Luchaco-Cullis and A. H. Hoveyda, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 8192.
22. A. Alexakis, C. Benhaim, S. Rosset and M. Humam, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 5262.
23. A. Rimkus and N. Sewald, *Org. Lett.*, 2003, **5**, 79.
24. M. S. Rasalkar, M. K. Potdar, S. S. Mohile and M. M. Salunkhe, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2005, **235**, 267.

25. R. S. Raghuvanshi and K. N. Singh, *Synth. Commun.*, 2006, **36**, 3075; R. S. Raghuvanshi and K. N. Singh, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, **37**, 1371; R. S. Raghuvanshi and K. N. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2008, **47**, 1735; R. S. Raghuvanshi and K. N. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2009, **48**, 1161.
26. A. A. Frimer, Organic Reactions involving the Superoxide Anion, in "The Chemistry of Functional Groups, Peroxide", ed. S. Patai, John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, 1983, Chap. 14, pp. 429-461.
27. K. N. Singh, R. S. Raghuvanshi and M. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2007, **46**, 829.